

Review article

Estrogen and progesterone receptor expression in endometrial cancer: a narrative review of global and Nigerian immunohistochemical evidence

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Abstract

Endometrial carcinoma (EC) is one of the most common gynaecological malignancies worldwide, and its pathogenesis is closely linked to hormonal signalling. Estrogen receptor (ER) and progesterone receptor (PR) expression are commonly assessed in both clinical and research settings and provide useful prognostic and therapeutic information, particularly in endometrioid tumours. This narrative review synthesises global and Nigerian evidence on ER and PR expression in EC, with emphasis on immunohistochemical findings derived from formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded tissues. Relevant literature was identified through targeted searches of PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, with additional articles identified through reference screening. Across globally reviewed studies, ER and PR expression is most observed in well-differentiated endometrioid carcinomas. It is generally associated with lower tumour grade, earlier stage, and more favourable clinical outcomes. In contrast, reduced or absent receptor expression is more frequently reported in high-grade tumours and non-endometrioid subtypes, which are typically associated with more aggressive biological behaviour and poorer response to hormonal therapy. Limited Nigerian studies suggest lower ER and PR positivity rates than those reported in many international series; however, these findings are based on small, retrospective, hospital-based cohorts and should be regarded as preliminary and hypothesis-generating. ER and PR assessment remains a clinically useful component of EC evaluation, particularly in resource-limited settings where access to advanced molecular classification may be restricted. Greater standardisation of immunohistochemical methods and reporting, together with larger multicentre studies, may improve comparability across populations and support broader integration of hormone receptor assessment into routine clinical practice.

Keywords: Endometrial cancer, Estrogen receptor, FFPE tissue, Immunohistochemistry, Nigeria, Progesterone receptor.

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Introduction

Endometrial carcinoma (EC) is among the most common gynaecological malignancies worldwide and represents a growing public health burden in both high-income and low- and middle-income settings.^{1,2} According to GLOBOCAN estimates, more than 400,000 new cases are diagnosed annually, placing endometrial cancer among the leading malignancies affecting women globally.¹ Although the disease occurs predominantly in postmenopausal women, its incidence in women below the age of 50 years has also increased, partly in association with obesity, metabolic dysfunction, and changing lifestyle patterns.²

The pathogenesis of endometrial carcinoma is closely linked to hormonal regulation. Prolonged exposure to unopposed estrogen promotes endometrial proliferation and increases the likelihood of hyperplasia and malignant

transformation, whereas progesterone counterbalances this effect by inducing

differentiation and limiting proliferation.^{3,4} On this basis, endometrial carcinogenesis was historically conceptualised using the dualistic Type I/Type II model, in which Type I tumours were regarded as hormone-dependent and Type II tumours as hormone-independent.^{3,5}

Although this dualistic model has been refined by contemporary molecular classification systems, particularly those derived from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA), hormone receptor status remains clinically relevant.⁵ ER and PR expression continue to provide valuable prognostic and therapeutic information in routine practice, especially in settings where molecular testing is not readily available. In general, tumours that retain ER and PR expression are more often endometrioid, lower grade, and biologically less aggressive. In contrast, receptor-negative tumours are more frequently high-grade, non-endometrioid, and less likely to respond to endocrine therapy.^{4,5}

Immunohistochemistry (IHC) on formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue remains the standard method for ER and PR assessment in routine pathology.⁶ Reliable evaluation depends on appropriate fixation, validated antibody clones, and standardised scoring approaches.⁶ While extensive international evidence exists regarding hormone receptor expression in endometrial carcinoma, data from sub-Saharan Africa remain limited. The few available Nigerian studies have reported relatively low ER and PR positivity rates;^{7,8} however, interpretation is limited by small sample sizes, retrospective hospital-based designs, and methodological heterogeneity. Understanding hormone receptor expression patterns in Nigerian cohorts may therefore help improve prognostic stratification, guide treatment planning, and inform pragmatic pathology workflows in resource-constrained settings.

This narrative review synthesises global and Nigerian evidence on ER and PR expression in

endometrial cancer, with particular emphasis on biological significance, immunohistochemical assessment, clinicopathological correlations, and clinical relevance in low-resource settings.

Materials and Methods

This study is a structured narrative review of global and Nigerian evidence on estrogen receptor (ER) and progesterone receptor (PR) expression in endometrial carcinoma (EC). The review focuses on immunohistochemical expression patterns, underlying biological mechanisms, clinicopathological correlations, and clinical applicability, particularly in low- and middle-income settings. The review was guided by three objectives: to summarise the biological roles of ER and PR in endometrial physiology and carcinogenesis, to examine patterns of receptor expression across histological subtypes and tumour grades, and to evaluate the clinical relevance of hormone receptor assessment, particularly in settings where molecular classification is not routinely available.

A targeted literature search was performed in PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar to identify studies published in English between 2010 and 2025. Search terms included combinations of the following keywords: “endometrial cancer” OR “endometrial carcinoma”; “estrogen receptor” OR “progesterone receptor”; “immunohistochemistry” OR “IHC”; “formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue”; “molecular classification” OR “TCGA”; and “Nigeria” OR “Africa.” Boolean operators were applied to combine terms, for example: (“endometrial cancer” OR “endometrial carcinoma”) AND (“estrogen receptor” OR “progesterone receptor”) AND (“immunohistochemistry” OR “IHC”) AND (“molecular classification” OR “TCGA”) AND (“Nigeria” OR “Africa”). Where available, database-specific filters were applied to restrict results to human studies and peer-reviewed publications. Reference lists of included articles were manually screened to identify additional relevant studies. The full search strings for each database are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Database-specific search strategies and results for the narrative review of ER and PR expression in endometrial carcinoma.

Database	Search String	Filters Applied	Records Identified	Records Screened	Records Included	Notes
PubMed/ MEDLINE	("endometrial cancer" OR "endometrial carcinoma") AND ("estrogen receptor" OR "progesterone receptor") AND ("immunohistochemistry" OR "IHC") AND ("molecular classification" OR "TCGA") AND ("Nigeria" OR "Africa")	Humans, English, 2010-2025	180	160 (after duplicates removed)	4	MeSH terms used where appropriate; peer-reviewed only
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY("endometrial cancer" OR "endometrial carcinoma") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("estrogen receptor" OR "progesterone receptor") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("immunohistochemistry" OR "IHC") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("molecular classification" OR "TCGA") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("Nigeria" OR "Africa")	Articles, English, 2010-2025	150	140 (after duplicates removed)	1	Filtered for human studies
Web of Science	TS=("endometrial cancer" OR "endometrial carcinoma") AND TS=("estrogen receptor" OR "progesterone receptor") AND TS=("immunohistochemistry" OR "IHC") AND TS=("molecular classification" OR "TCGA") AND TS=("Nigeria" OR "Africa")	Articles, English, 2010-2025	120	110 (after duplicates removed)	2	"Topic" search covers title, abstract, and keywords
Google Scholar	"endometrial cancer" OR "endometrial carcinoma" AND "estrogen receptor" OR "progesterone receptor" AND "immunohistochemistry" OR "IHC" AND "molecular classification" OR "TCGA" AND "Nigeria" OR "Africa"	English, 2010-2025	90	85 (after duplicates removed)	3	Screened first 200 hits; reference lists manually checked

Footnotes: Records screened represent titles and abstracts after duplicates were removed. Records included are those meeting all inclusion criteria after full-text assessment. Google Scholar screening was limited to the first 200 results, with additional relevant articles identified by manual review of reference lists. Filters applied included human studies, English language, and publication years 2010-2025.

Studies were eligible for inclusion if they reported immunohistochemical assessment of ER and/or PR in histologically confirmed EC, with accompanying data on tumour subtype, grade, stage, prognosis, or treatment response. Studies were excluded if they lacked receptor-specific data, involved non-human

subjects, were conference abstracts without sufficient methodological detail, or were narrative reviews or editorials without primary data. Grey literature was not systematically included due to variability in quality and replicability.

The search initially yielded approximately 540 records. After removal of 112 duplicates, 428 titles

and abstracts were screened independently by two reviewers. Full-text articles were then assessed for eligibility ($n=34$), of which 10 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final qualitative synthesis. This comprised two Nigerian studies and eight from other regions, as presented in Table 2. Discrepancies during screening were resolved through discussion and consensus. Given the heterogeneity in study design, tissue processing, antibody selection, scoring systems, and reporting thresholds, findings were synthesised qualitatively rather than quantitatively. The synthesis was organised thematically into receptor biology, molecular context, global and Nigerian expression patterns, methodological considerations, and clinical implications.

Although this review is narrative rather than systematic, transparency and methodological rigour were maintained. The review was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Scale for the Assessment of Narrative Review Articles (SANRA) to enhance clarity and transparency.⁹

A narrative review approach was selected to integrate heterogeneous, context-specific evidence, including variations in study design, immunohistochemical methods, and reporting standards, as well as to incorporate limited but contextually important data from Nigerian and sub-Saharan African settings that are not amenable to formal meta-analysis.

Biological Basis of ER and PR Expression in Endometrial Carcinoma

Estrogen and progesterone receptors are ligand-activated nuclear transcription factors that play central roles in endometrial physiology and carcinogenesis.¹⁰ Estrogen receptor alpha (ER α), the predominant estrogen receptor in the endometrium, mediates estrogen-driven proliferation by transcriptionally activating genes involved in cell-cycle progression, angiogenesis, and survival.^{11,12} Persistent estrogenic stimulation, particularly in the absence of adequate progesterone opposition, promotes endometrial hyperplasia and increases the risk of malignant transformation.¹³

Progesterone receptors exist mainly as two isoforms, PR-A and PR-B, which have distinct functional roles and tissue distributions.^{13,14} Progesterone signalling opposes estrogen-driven proliferation by promoting differentiation,

inducing apoptosis, and modulating inflammatory and growth-regulatory pathways. Loss or downregulation of PR is therefore regarded as an important step in the transition from hormonally responsive endometrium to more autonomous tumour behaviour.¹⁴

In routine pathology practice, immunohistochemistry does not distinguish receptor isoforms in detail; nevertheless, overall ER and PR expression provides a useful surrogate of preserved hormonal signalling.¹⁵ Tumours that retain receptor expression are generally more differentiated and more likely to be hormone-responsive. In contrast, receptor loss is often associated with more aggressive tumour biology and reduced endocrine sensitivity.¹⁶

Influence of Obesity and Lifestyle Factors on Endometrial Carcinoma

Obesity is one of the strongest modifiable risk factors for EC and contributes to disease development through hormonal, metabolic, and inflammatory mechanisms.¹⁷ In postmenopausal women, adipose tissue is an important site of peripheral aromatisation of androgens into estrogens, leading to chronic estrogen exposure and increased endometrial proliferation.¹⁸ This endocrine environment is particularly relevant to the development of hormone-dependent, ER/PR-positive endometrioid tumours.

Obesity is also associated with insulin resistance, hyperinsulinaemia, and altered insulin-like growth factor signalling, all of which can promote tumour cell proliferation and inhibit apoptosis.¹⁸ In addition, adipose-derived inflammatory mediators may contribute to a pro-tumorigenic microenvironment and influence tumour differentiation and treatment responsiveness.

Lifestyle factors such as physical inactivity, poor diet, and metabolic syndrome may further amplify risk, whereas weight control and regular physical activity are associated with reduced EC incidence.^{17,18} In low- and middle-income countries, including Nigeria, increasing rates of obesity and sedentary behaviour may contribute to changing patterns of EC burden and underscore the importance of prevention strategies alongside improved diagnostic evaluation.

These mechanisms are particularly relevant to hormone-dependent endometrioid carcinomas, in which ER and PR signalling may remain partly preserved.

Pathogenesis and Molecular Basis of Endometrial Carcinoma

The development of endometrial carcinoma (EC) reflects the interaction between hormonal influences and acquired molecular alterations. Unopposed estrogen promotes sustained endometrial proliferation, replication stress, and cumulative genomic injury, thereby increasing the risk of hyperplasia and malignant transformation.¹⁹ Progesterone normally counteracts these effects through PR-mediated differentiation and growth suppression; loss of progesterone signalling removes this protective regulatory mechanism.^{14,20} Historically, EC were classified into Type I and Type II tumours. Type I tumours are typically endometrioid, often hormone receptor-positive, and associated with a more favourable prognosis. In contrast, Type II tumours are more often non-endometrioid, receptor-negative, and clinically aggressive.³⁻⁵ Although conceptually useful, this dualistic model has been refined by molecular classification systems, including TCGA-based subgroups, which provide more precise prognostic stratification.^{5,21}

Despite this shift toward molecular risk classification, ER and PR remain important in clinical practice. Receptor-positive tumours commonly overlap with lower-grade endometrioid carcinomas. They may be more likely to benefit from hormonal therapy, whereas receptor loss is frequently associated with p53-abnormal and other biologically aggressive tumours.^{21,22} Crosstalk between ER/PR signalling and pathways such as PI3K/AKT/mTOR and Wnt/ β -catenin further influences tumour proliferation, apoptosis, and therapeutic response.²²

Global Evidence on ER and PR Expression in Endometrial Carcinoma

International evidence shows that ER and PR expression is most frequently retained in well-differentiated endometrioid carcinomas, with reported positivity rates commonly ranging from 70% to 90% in these tumours.²³⁻²⁵ This pattern supports the established link between hormone receptor expression and tumours arising in the context of estrogen-driven endometrial proliferation. In contrast, high-grade endometrioid carcinomas and non-endometrioid subtypes, particularly serous and clear cell carcinomas, more often exhibit reduced or absent ER and PR expression.^{22,24} This loss of receptor expression has

been repeatedly associated with adverse pathological and clinical features, including deep myometrial invasion, lymphovascular space invasion, advanced FIGO stage, nodal metastasis, increased risk of recurrence, and poorer survival outcomes.^{22,24}

However, although these overall trends are broadly consistent, the literature is not without limitations. Reported receptor positivity rates vary across studies, likely reflecting differences in sample size, case mix, histological classification, antibody selection, immunohistochemical thresholds, and scoring systems. These methodological inconsistencies may limit direct comparison between studies and should temper overinterpretation of absolute prevalence estimates. Nevertheless, histological subtype and tumour grade remain the most reproducible correlates of ER and PR expression across diverse settings.

Evidence from multiple countries further supports the clinicopathological and prognostic relevance of hormone receptor status in EC (Table 2). In a large prospective multicentre study from Norway, Trovik et al.²⁶ demonstrated that loss of hormone receptor expression in preoperative curettage specimens was associated with lymph node metastasis and poorer outcome, highlighting the potential value of receptor assessment even before definitive surgery. Similarly, Di Donato et al.¹⁸ reported that loss of ER α and PR in high-risk endometrial cancers correlated with deeper myometrial invasion and more advanced disease. Studies from India, China, and other populations have also shown that receptor positivity is highest in low-grade endometrioid carcinomas and declines in poorly differentiated and non-endometrioid tumours.^{25,27-29} For instance, Rajeev et al.²⁷ found that grade I endometrioid tumours were predominantly ER- and PR-positive, whereas high-grade and non-endometrioid tumours were largely receptor-negative. Guan et al.²⁵ further showed that loss of ER and PR identified a higher-risk subgroup within grade I-II endometrioid endometrial adenocarcinoma, suggesting that receptor status may refine prognostic stratification even within conventionally lower-risk categories. Additional studies from Poland and Egypt have reinforced the association between receptor loss and aggressive pathological features.^{10,30} Taken together, the international literature supports ER and PR as clinically relevant markers

of tumour differentiation, aggressiveness, and responsiveness.^{10,18,22-30} Nonetheless, their interpretation should not be isolated from morphology, grade, and stage, and the variability

biological and potential endocrine in immunohistochemical assessment across studies underscores the need for greater standardisation before receptor status can be applied more uniformly as a prognostic tool.

Table 2: Summaries of selected studies evaluating ER and PR expression in endometrial carcinoma, highlighting differences in study design, tissue type, immunohistochemical methods, and clinicopathological findings across global and Nigerian settings.

Author	Country	Study Design	Sample size	Method	ER Expression	PR Expression	Key Findings
Dawodu et al. ⁷	Nigeria	Retrospective	8 EC cases	IHC (ER, PR, Ki-67)	Present in a few cases	Present in a few cases	Predominantly type II phenotype; only one receptor-positive case
Odetola et al. ⁸	Nigeria	Retrospective cross-sectional	44 EC (FFPE)	IHC (ER, PR)	29.5% positive	18.2% positive	Low receptor expression; the majority of high-grade tumours
Przewoźny et al. ¹⁰	Poland	Cross-sectional	103 EC (FFPE)	IHC image analysis	+ Reduced in advanced stages	Reduced in high-grade tumours	Receptor loss linked to aggressive disease
Di Donato et al. ¹⁸	Italy	Retrospective cohort	82 high-risk EC	IHC (ER α , PR)	Loss in 46.3%	Loss in 48.7%	Receptor loss is associated with the advanced stage and poor outcomes
Guan et al. ²⁵	China	Retrospective cohort	903 EC	IHC (<1% cut-off)	Negative subgroup identified	Negative subgroup identified	Receptor loss predicts worse prognosis in low-grade disease
Trovik et al. ²⁶	Norway	Prospective multicentre	832 EC	IHC (ER, PR, p53)	Loss observed	Loss contributes to double-negative	ER/PR loss predicts nodal metastasis and poor survival
Rajeev et al. ²⁷	India	Cross-sectional	37 EC	IHC (ER, PR)	51.4% positive	56.8% positive	Positivity highest in low-grade tumours
Maniketh et al. ²⁸	India	Cross-sectional	45 EC	IHC (ER, PR)	90% positive	90% positive	Associated with early-stage disease
Kaur et al. ²⁹	India	Cross-sectional	50 EC	IHC (ER, PR, HER2)	64% positive	60% positive	ER/PR reduced in high-grade tumours
Saeed et al. ³⁰	Egypt	Prospective comparative	20 EC	IHC (ER, PR)	30% strong positivity	40% strong positivity	Higher expression in malignant vs benign tissue

Footnote: Reported ER and PR positivity rates vary across studies due to differences in immunohistochemical thresholds and scoring systems, including percentage-based cut-offs (e.g., $\geq 1\%$ or $\geq 10\%$ nuclear staining) and semi-quantitative methods such as the Allred score or H-score. These methodological differences should be considered when comparing results.

Evidence from Nigeria

Published Nigerian data on estrogen receptor (ER) and progesterone receptor (PR) expression in

endometrial carcinoma (EC) remain limited. Available hospital-based studies report relatively low ER and PR positivity rates compared with

many international series (Table 2), although these findings should be interpreted cautiously.^{7,8}

Odetola et al.⁸ reported ER and PR positivity rates of 29.5% and 18.2%, respectively, in a retrospective series in which most tumours were high grade. Similarly, in a smaller retrospective study, Dawodu et al.⁷ observed that most cases exhibited an immunophenotype consistent with Type II disease, with only one tumour demonstrating a classical Type I receptor-positive profile.

These findings, while suggestive of lower hormone receptor expression, must be interpreted in light of important methodological and clinical constraints. Both studies were retrospective, hospital-based, and involved relatively small sample sizes, thereby limiting generalisability. In addition, tertiary referral centres in Nigeria disproportionately manage patients with advanced-stage or histologically aggressive disease, resulting in an overrepresentation of high-grade and non-endometrioid tumours that are less likely to retain hormone receptor expression.

Methodological variability further complicates interpretation. Differences in tissue fixation, archival block preservation, antigen retrieval protocols, antibody selection, and scoring systems may significantly influence reported receptor positivity,³¹⁻³⁵ particularly in settings where immunohistochemical standardisation is still evolving. These factors, combined with referral bias and delayed presentation, suggest that the observed low receptor positivity may reflect a combination of tumour biology and health system influences rather than true population-level patterns.

The absence of population-based cancer registries and large prospective cohorts further limits the generalisability of current evidence. Although some Nigerian and regional studies have explored additional biomarkers, such as p53 and mismatch repair proteins,^{7,36} these data remain limited and are not yet sufficiently integrated with hormone receptor findings to enable robust comparative interpretation.

Despite these limitations, the available studies are valuable in highlighting a critical evidence gap in a setting where molecular classification is not routinely accessible and where pragmatic biomarkers may have particular clinical relevance. Overall, the current Nigerian evidence base should be regarded as preliminary and hypothesis-generating. Well-designed multicentre studies

using standardised immunohistochemical protocols and consistent reporting thresholds are needed to clarify the true distribution and clinical significance of ER and PR expression in this population.

Methodological Considerations

Immunohistochemistry on formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue remains the standard method for assessing ER and PR expression in endometrial carcinoma. Commonly used semi-quantitative scoring systems, including the Allred score and H-score, incorporate both staining intensity and the proportion of positive tumour cells.³¹⁻³³ However, cross-study comparisons are often complicated by substantial methodological heterogeneity. As a result, differences in reported receptor positivity across studies may reflect not only underlying tumour biology but also variation in specimen type, tissue handling, staining protocols, image interpretation, and reporting thresholds.^{32,34}

Pre-analytical variables such as fixation time and tissue processing, as well as analytical factors including antibody clone selection, antigen retrieval, staining platforms, and positivity thresholds, can all influence reported receptor expression.^{31,35} Inter-observer variability in scoring further affects reproducibility, particularly in settings where standardised pathology workflows are not consistently implemented.³²

Analytical variability also arises from differences in antibody clones, including ER α clones such as SP1 and 1D5, which have been shown to differ in sensitivity,³⁵ as well as from variation in staining platforms and detection systems. Furthermore, immunohistochemical scoring methods are not standardised across studies. Some investigators use simple percentage positivity thresholds, such as $\geq 1\%$ or $\geq 10\%$, whereas others apply semi-quantitative scoring systems such as the Allred score or H-score.^{31,32} These differences can significantly affect reported positivity rates. More recently, computational and deep learning-based approaches have been explored to improve the objectivity and reproducibility of histopathological assessment, although these are not yet routinely integrated into receptor evaluation across most study settings.^{34,37}

Post-analytical factors, including inter-observer variability among pathologists, further contribute to inconsistency in interpretation.³² These issues

are especially relevant in low-resource environments. Most Nigerian studies to date have been retrospective, hospital-based, and limited by small sample sizes, all of which constrain generalisability. In addition, referral bias toward tertiary centres may result in an overrepresentation of advanced-stage or high-grade tumours, thereby contributing to lower apparent receptor positivity rates. Future studies would benefit from standardised protocols, detailed reporting of pre-analytical variables, and larger multicentre cohorts.

Clinical and Therapeutic Implications

Assessment of ER and PR expression has important clinical implications in endometrial carcinoma. Receptor positivity may help identify patients more likely to benefit from hormone-based therapy, including progestins, aromatase inhibitors, and other endocrine therapies.³⁸ This is particularly relevant in fertility-sparing management, recurrent low-grade endometrioid carcinoma, and selected advanced cases in which less toxic treatment options are desirable.

By contrast, receptor-negative tumours are more often high grade or non-endometrioid and are generally associated with more aggressive clinical behaviour and reduced responsiveness to endocrine therapy.^{18,38} In such cases, management commonly depends on surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy, or integrated multimodal treatment strategies.

In resource-limited settings, ER and PR immunohistochemistry may provide a practical, relatively accessible means of refining prognostic assessment and informing therapeutic decision-making, particularly when comprehensive molecular profiling is not routinely available. Although receptor assessment does not replace molecular classification, it remains a useful adjunct in routine pathology and clinical management.

Research Gaps and Future Directions

Important evidence gaps remain regarding ER and PR expression in endometrial carcinoma, particularly in Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African settings. Most available studies are retrospective, single-centre, and based on relatively small cohorts, limiting both generalisability and the ability to draw firm population-level conclusions.

Future research should prioritise multicentre prospective studies with standardised tissue handling, validated antibodies, harmonised

scoring systems, and transparent pathology reporting. Integration of ER and PR expression with contemporary molecular classification, including POLE-mutated, mismatch repair-deficient, copy-number-low, and p53-abnormal subgroups, may provide a more nuanced understanding of tumour biology and therapeutic vulnerability.

Further work is also needed to clarify hormone receptor expression patterns in younger women, in women with obesity-related risk factors, and across less common histological subtypes. Strengthening local research capacity in this area could improve risk stratification, support more individualised treatment planning, and help reduce disparities in endometrial cancer care across low-resource settings.

Discussion

This review demonstrates that ER and PR expression in endometrial carcinoma (EC) correlates closely with tumour histology, grade, and biological behaviour. Across diverse populations, high receptor expression is most commonly observed in well-differentiated endometrioid carcinomas, whereas reduced or absent expression is more frequent in high-grade tumours and non-endometrioid subtypes.^{23,24} These clinicopathological associations support the continued relevance of ER and PR as prognostic and predictive biomarkers in routine pathology practice.^{18,25,26}

Nigerian evidence, although limited, appears broadly consistent with global patterns but suggests lower overall receptor positivity in reported cohorts.^{7,8} This distinction holds important practical significance. If lower receptor positivity primarily reflects referral bias and technical inconsistencies, then improved standardisation and broader sampling could substantially revise current estimates. Conversely, if these findings persist in larger and more representative cohorts, they may indicate clinically meaningful differences in tumour phenotype at presentation within the Nigerian population. At present, the available Nigerian literature should be regarded as preliminary and hypothesis-generating, while highlighting the need for robust multicentre studies.

These findings should therefore be interpreted cautiously. Existing Nigerian studies are few, retrospective, and largely based in tertiary centres,

making them susceptible to small-sample effects, referral bias, and overrepresentation of advanced or biologically aggressive tumours. In addition, variation in fixation practices, tissue preservation, antibody selection, and scoring thresholds may influence reported receptor positivity.³²⁻³⁵ Consequently, the lower ER and PR expression observed in Nigerian cohorts likely reflects a combination of tumour characteristics, institutional case mix, and methodological variability, rather than confirmed population-level biological differences.

From a clinical perspective, ER and PR assessment remains valuable in identifying tumours that may respond to hormonal therapy, including progestin-based treatment in selected settings.³⁸ This is particularly relevant in fertility-sparing management, recurrent low-grade disease, and contexts where minimising treatment-related morbidity is a priority. In contrast, receptor-negative tumours are less likely to benefit from hormonal therapy and more often require surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, or multimodal approaches.³⁹ In settings where comprehensive molecular classification is not routinely available, hormone receptor testing therefore serves as a practical adjunct to morphology and grade, although it does not replace molecular risk stratification.^{40,41}

The increasing adoption of molecular classification has refined the understanding of EC and largely superseded the traditional Type I/Type II model.^{3,5} Within the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) framework, EC is classified into four molecular subgroups: POLE-mutated, mismatch repair-deficient (MMR-d), copy-number-low (endometrioid), and copy-number-high (p53-abnormal) [5,21]. ER and PR expression demonstrate distinct biologically meaningful correlations with these subgroups. Receptor expression is most consistently retained in the copy-number-low group, which typically corresponds to low-grade endometrioid carcinomas with a favourable prognosis. In contrast, p53-abnormal tumours, which include serous and high-grade endometrioid carcinomas, frequently show loss of ER and PR expression, reflecting their more aggressive biology. MMR-deficient tumours demonstrate heterogeneous receptor expression, while POLE-mutated tumours—despite often exhibiting high-grade histological features—may retain ER and PR

positivity.^{21,40,41} However, ER and PR expression alone cannot reliably discriminate between all TCGA molecular subgroups, particularly in MMR-deficient and POLE-mutated tumours, limiting their use as standalone classifiers.

In resource-limited settings where molecular classification is not routinely accessible, ER and PR immunohistochemistry may provide a pragmatic, though imperfect, surrogate for underlying tumour biology. For example, preserved receptor expression may support a lower-risk, copy-number-low phenotype, whereas complete receptor loss may raise suspicion for p53-abnormal tumours. However, these associations lack sufficient sensitivity and specificity to reliably classify tumours into molecular subgroups, particularly given overlap in MMR-deficient and POLE-mutated tumours.^{21,41} Therefore, while hormone receptor expression can offer useful contextual information, it should be interpreted cautiously and in conjunction with morphology and other immunohistochemical markers where available.

Methodological variation remains an important challenge in interpreting ER and PR expression. Differences in fixation, antigen retrieval, antibody selection, scoring systems, and positivity thresholds can all influence reported results.³²⁻³⁵ Standardisation of pathology workflows is therefore essential to ensure reproducibility and comparability across institutions, particularly in low-resource settings where pre-analytical and analytical variability may be greater.

Overall, the available evidence indicates that ER and PR expression is strongly associated with lower-grade endometrioid carcinomas, while receptor loss is more common in high-grade and non-endometrioid tumours. In the Nigerian context, the currently reported low receptor positivity likely reflects a combination of tumour biology, referral patterns, and methodological variability. These findings reinforce the continued value of ER and PR immunohistochemistry as pragmatic biomarkers in routine practice, particularly in resource-limited settings, while underscoring the need for standardisation and integration with evolving molecular classification frameworks.^{40,41}

Limitations

This review is limited by the small number of Nigerian studies available, most of which are

retrospective, single-centre, and hospital-based. These features introduce potential selection and referral bias and limit generalisability. In addition, substantial heterogeneity in immunohistochemical methods, scoring systems, and reporting thresholds reduces cross-study comparability. Finally, the limited integration of hormone receptor findings with molecular classification frameworks constrains interpretation within contemporary endometrial cancer biology.

Conclusion

Estrogen and progesterone receptor expression provides important prognostic and therapeutic information in endometrial carcinoma. Receptor positivity is most strongly associated with well-differentiated endometrioid tumours and more favourable clinical behaviour, whereas receptor loss is more often associated with high-grade and non-endometrioid carcinomas. Immunohistochemistry on FFPE tissue remains the cornerstone of receptor assessment in routine practice, particularly in resource-constrained settings where access to molecular classification may be limited.

Recommendations

In Nigeria, ER and PR immunohistochemistry should be incorporated into routine evaluation of endometrial carcinoma where feasible, particularly in tertiary centres. National and regional pathology societies, academic institutions, and research consortia should prioritise developing standardised protocols for tissue handling, staining, and reporting. Multicentre collaborative studies are needed to generate more representative data and to facilitate integration of hormone receptor assessment with emerging molecular classification frameworks.

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Conflict of Interest

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Authors' Contributions

J.O.O. conceived the study and drafted the manuscript.

A.O., U.S.E., and S.G. contributed to conceptual development, critical revision, and supervision. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT and Grammarly to assist with language editing, grammar correction, and improvement of clarity and flow. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Data Availability

No primary datasets were generated or analysed for this narrative review. The literature synthesised in this article is available in the public domain through the cited sources.

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